

THE IMPACT OF GREEN MARKETING ON CONSUMERS' ATTITUDES IN THE CONSTRUCTION BUSINESS IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

Sustainable development, going green, green strategies, have become a natural part in our everyday life. There are a lot of businesses on the market, which play an important role in countries economic development and construction business is among them. It is a backbone business in Georgia, which is facing a lot of challenges beginning from the green strategies up to the national regulations and policies as well. Day by day as sustainability becomes more actual companies also started to build green buildings, with integrated energy efficiency systems, which gives customers to live in ecologically safe environment, save the money on the bills and invest money on a long-term period. The aim of the article is to explore the relationship between green marketing and consumer attitudes toward sustainable building practices, investigate the factors influencing consumer perceptions and preferences regarding green marketing initiatives in the construction industry and explore the impact of green marketing strategies on consumer purchase intentions and decision-making processes related to construction-related products and services and create the profile of potential consumer. The study uses quantitative research using questionnaires. In conclusion, it can be said, that green marketing is not the main and most important factor affecting purchase intentions of Georgian customers, but they pay attention to it and are ready to pay more for "green buildings."

Keywords: Green Marketing; Green buildings; Purchase intentions.

JEL classification: Q01 - Sustainable Development; L74 – Construction; L85 - Real Estate Services

Introduction

In the modern world, where taking care for the environment has become a very urgent issue the construction industry is in the center of special attention, because it can have a significant (positive and negative) impact on the environmental sustainability. As consumers become increasingly aware of environmental issues, their attitudes and preferences towards the use of sustainable practices in the construction business are changing, so nowadays the construction industry is experiencing a surge in the demand for eco-friendly building materials. This trend has given rise to "green marketing". Green marketing has emerged as a powerful strategy to influence consumer perceptions, choices and behaviors in the construction industry. This paper aims to examine the impact of green marketing on consumer attitudes in the construction business.

The construction industry is recognized as a significant source of environmental degradation, resource depletion and carbon emissions. In response to these challenges, there has been increased interest in sustainable construction practices that reduce the environmental footprint of construction industry. Green marketing, which includes a variety of strategies and communication techniques, seeks to promote the development of sustainable products, services and practices in the construction sector. Understanding the impact of green marketing on consumer attitudes is critical to promoting positive change and implementing sustainable construction practices. The main challenge for every successful company is to aim the strategy to the right target market and have an ability to follow their demands and satisfy them.

The central hypothesis of this study is that green marketing has a positive effect on the purchase intentions of Georgian consumers in the construction industry. To investigate this hypothesis, the following objectives were set:

- Exploring the relationship between green marketing and consumer attitudes toward sustainable building practices;
- Investigating the factors influencing consumer perceptions and preferences regarding green marketing initiatives in the construction industry;
- Exploring the impact of green marketing on consumer purchase intentions and decision-making processes related to construction-related products and services.
- Create the profile of potential customers.

Although there are studies on the impact of green marketing in various industries, the construction sector is relatively less studied in this regard in Georgia. Firstly, this paper examines factors that influence consumer attitudes toward green marketing initiatives, providing valuable insights for construction businesses seeking to develop effective marketing strategies. Secondly, by analyzing the relationship between green marketing and consumer purchase intentions, this study provides practical implications for marketers aiming to promote sustainable products and services in the construction industry and thirdly according the research the study creates the profile of potential customers, which are intended to buy real estate.

Additionally, identifying key factors and communication approaches that shape consumer attitudes will help construction businesses align their practices with

target market expectations. The research also has highlighted several target groups (e.g. by education; by income).

As social and environmental problems are becoming more and more actual it is essential for the construction companies to implement green marketing strategies and highlight the benefits of it, rising awareness in the context of sustainability and green construction.

Literature review

The study of green buildings and their marketing is not old. Interest towards it have increased in recent years. According to Zhao et al. (2015), green building represents a significant shift in the building industry. Green buildings reduce their negative environmental effects while improving occupant health and return on investment for investors and communities by incorporating life cycle considerations into their design and development, according to Robichaud and Anantamula (2010). Agbajor and Mewomo (2022) present a synthesis of the scholarly investigation into green building research in South Africa. According to the study's findings, green building projects are experiencing uneven growth, as well as motivations, challenges and socio-economic difficulties that nations face when attempting to do so. To maximize the growth of green building in the region, this study recommends adoption of finance plans, the use of cutting-edge technologies (Lashkhi, 2022; Lashkhi et al., 2022) and promotion of green and sustainable building curriculum in all institutions. According to Zuo and Zhao (2014), studies on green buildings can be divided into three main categories. The three areas include information about and definition of green buildings, describing of strategies and procedures for producing green buildings and outlining the advantages and disadvantages of green buildings quantitatively. Kinnunen et al (2022) found that increased marketing efforts and actions lead to better sustainability performance, as do greater eco-innovation capacities. In addition, the results indicate that a company with superior eco-innovation capabilities is more likely to have a high brand value.

It is believed, that people concerned with the environmental issues could be affected by green marketing campaign in the construction industry as well. There are a number of motivational values that consumers can use to purchase and demand green buildings, according to Joachim et al. (2015), such as conservation of natural resources, energy efficiency, water quality, maintenance costs and environmental impact, among others. All of these motives may result in environmental behavior and attitude due to the connection between values and how people interact with their environment. As Joshi et al. (2015) indicate, social references can positively impact consumers' propensity for making green purchases. It is appropriate to state that social references can positively impact the intention to purchase green buildings. According to the research made by Kirby and Delai (2016) the following nine variables were associated with the content of the selected articles: environmental attitude, purchase intention, physical attributes, social references, perceived behavior control,

perceived identity, motivation values, price and demographics. Mansour and Radford examine Peattie's (2001) green purchasing perception matrix to gain a deeper understanding of how building occupants perceive green-labeled buildings. An analytical approach has been used to determine the influence factors of the Stimulus Organism Model and Schema Congruity concepts from consumer behavior studies. As a result, the authors suggest a sense of green buildings. In green buildings, tenants may be willing to tolerate a certain level of compromise, while building systems may actually be having a positive impact on the environment. Harmadi et al. (2023) aimed to investigate and analyze consumer satisfaction factors and how they affect consumer loyalty towards green products. According to their studies, both service quality and brand perception positively impact customer happiness. Weniger et al (2023) tried to determine how sustainability-related factors influence the purchasing decisions of private individuals as end users in German construction industry. Findings indicate that although customers are generally interested in sustainable building goods, they do not have a comprehensive understanding of the term. The environment often takes precedence over economics and social factors. Since private individuals rarely make purchasing decisions in the construction sector, it is the responsibility of the entire construction industry to create a system that allows consumers to easily and quickly access clear information about sustainable products. Saini (2013) investigates how green marketing affects consumer purchasing behavior, how businesses can gain a competitive edge by using it and what obstacles businesses may face in adopting green marketing practices. A research study conducted in Delhi's Rohini neighborhood demonstrates that businesses need to communicate with customers more in order to go green. Also, pricing and quality are more important than „environmental responsibility". Abashidze (2022) states that a user's behavior patterns can differ based on the type of platform the company uses. It is important for marketers to remember that a considerable portion of social media users use multiple social media platforms. Marketers have to differentiate their advertising tactics, commitment levels and objectives according to the different types of social media platforms.

Authors studying this topic use various research methods in their papers. Simpeh and Smallwood (2021) studied crucial factors influencing green building in the South African construction industry by looking at the concept of green building. A questionnaire survey was used to collect data from randomly selected construction industry professionals in South Africa using a quantitative approach. A descriptive (mean) and an inferential (one way analysis) analysis was used to analyze the data. According to the findings, green construction is hindered by a lack of incentives for promotion, a lack of cost data and a lack of information about the prospects and financial and economic advantages of green buildings. Correia et al. (2023) aim to determine whether consumers' attention to green marketing messages affects their likelihood of making green purchases. Additionally, the study examines how consumer behavior and preferences affect the amount of

attention consumers pay to green marketing communications, including gender, education and environmental attitudes. As part of the data analysis, descriptive analyses, parametric and nonparametric testing, linear correlation and regression analyses were used. Findings indicate that businesses' green marketing messages are well received by customers. Consumers' attention to green marketing communications was strongly correlated with their green purchase behaviors. The findings also support the notion that people with higher levels of education (Kvirkvaia et al., 2018), pro-environmental attitudes and females are more receptive to businesses' green marketing messages. Hassin, Surt, and Sears (2012) emphasize the importance of metrics in evaluating the impact of green marketing strategies, which should improve the potential for environmental and social outcomes.

Going green and being more sustainable is considered to be a good way for economic development as well. At the moment country experiences some serious economic problems. According to Daghelishvili (2016) in addition to poor access to capital, a lack of a wide range of commodities, difficulties obtaining materials, a lack of highly developed technology domains, insufficient infrastructure, etc., there are many other challenges in Georgia's economy. Going green in various industries of the country could be a good way to attract FDI and increase standards of consumers in the country. Barak et al. (2022) state that as a result of rising income inequality and non-renewable energy consumption per person, poverty is decreased by rising growth and renewable energy consumption per person. In light of the findings, authorities should develop an energy strategy that emphasizes the need for renewable energy and energy-efficient technology in an economy. Charaia (2014, 2020) state that although adhering to EU standards in a short amount of time will be expensive for both the Georgian government and the business, it will be extremely beneficial in the long run from a sustainable point of view.

Materials and methods

The research was conducted using materials provided by research papers and literature reviews as well as books of Georgian and foreign scientists. Furthermore, quantitative research (structured questionnaire was developed) method was used to obtain information about consumer attitudes towards green marketing in the construction industry.

The target segment of construction sector customers was selected for data collection. The sample was selected by random sampling. The sample represents a diverse range of demographic characteristics, including age, gender and education. 110 people took part in the survey, from which 104 answers were valid. These

were randomly selected respondents, who had an intention to buy a house. This was the filter question and in case of answering it positively participants had ability to continue filling the rested questionnaire.

Data were collected using online surveys that were distributed through various platforms such as social media, online forums and email invitations. Participants were given clear instructions on how to complete the questionnaire. The confidentiality of the respondents is ensured.

The collected data was analyzed using quantitative techniques. Quantitative data from Likert scale questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, crosstabulation, T test, means and standard deviations. Correlation analysis and regression analysis will be used to study the relationships between variables.

Ethical considerations are taken into account and informed consent is obtained from all participants and their identities are kept confidential.

Based on the literature review following variables were incorporated in research model: Ecologically clean environment, Marketing campaign, Quality, Recommendation, Healthier construction materials, Architecture, Price, Location, Interest rate, green building.

The dependent variable is purchasing intention, reflecting consumer's willingness to purchase a product (house) from construction company. Accordingly, regression formula was defined as follows:

$$\text{Purchase Intention} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Company trust}) + \beta_2(\text{Social environment}) + \beta_3(\text{Safe environment}) + \beta_4(\text{Ecologically clean environment}) + \beta_5(\text{Marketing campaign}) + \beta_6(\text{Quality}) + \beta_7(\text{Recommendation}) + \beta_8(\text{Healthier construction materials}) + \beta_9(\text{Architecture}) + \beta_{10}(\text{Price}) + \beta_{11}(\text{Location}) + \beta_{12}(\text{Interest rate}) + \beta_{13}(\text{Green building}) + \epsilon$$

ϵ represents the error term or residual, which accounts for the unexplained variation in consumers' attitudes towards green marketing. It captures any factors not accounted for by the independent variables and the regression equation.

Results and discussions

The collected data was analyzed in MS Excel and SPSS. In the research took part 110 people (from which valid was 104 as they have answered the first filter question positively). The results are demonstrated below. As the Table 1.

Gender demonstrates in the research took part 104 people, from which 56.7% (59) were females and 43.3% (45) males.

Table 1.

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	59	56.7	56.7	56.7
	Male	45	43.3	43.3	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

According to the Table 2. Age - 4.8% were 18 - 24 years; 19.2% – 25-34 years; 40.40% – 35-44 years; 26.9% - 45-54 years; 8.7% - 55+ years. It shows that most of the people who

have recently bought the real estate, where from 35-44 years old, so they can be considered as target markets for real estate’s sellers.

Table 2.

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-24	5	4.8	4.8	4.8
	25-34	20	19.2	19.2	24.0
	35-44	42	40.4	40.4	64.4
	45-54	28	26.9	26.9	91.3
	55+	9	8.7	8.7	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors’ according to the research

As the Table 3. Education demonstrates, people who have intention to buy a house are mostly holding masters’ degree

60.60%, then comes bachelor’s degree 26.9%, PhD 10.5% and secondary education 1.9%.

Table 3.

		Education			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachelor	28	26.9	26.9	26.9
	Master	63	60.6	60.6	87.5
	PhD	11	10.6	10.6	98.1
	Secondary ed.	2	1.9	1.9	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors’ according to the research

As the Table 4. Occupation shows, most of the participants were working full time, 11.5% were self-employed,

part time were working 6.7% and unemployed were 2.9%.

Table 4.

		Occupation			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Full time	82	78.8	78.8	78.8
	Part time	7	6.7	6.7	85.6
	Self employed	12	11.5	11.5	97.1
	Unemployed	3	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors’ according to the research

Table 5.

		Number on family members			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	21	20.2	20.2	20.2
	2	35	33.7	33.7	53.8
	3	28	26.9	26.9	80.8
	4	10	9.6	9.6	90.4
	5 and more	3	2.9	2.9	93.3
	I live alone	7	6.7	6.7	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors’ according to the research

The collected date showed that people who are motivated to buy real estate, are having two family members 33.7% (Table 5.

Number on family members), this is logical, because buying house is commonly actual when the family is growing.

Table 6.

		Monthly Income			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0 – 500	2	1.9	1.9	1.9
	501 – 1000	4	3.8	3.8	100.0
	1001 – 1500	15	14.4	14.4	16.3
	1501 – 2000	25	24.0	24.0	40.4
	2000 +	58	55.8	55.8	96.2
Total		104	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

What about income 55.8% of the research participants were having more than 2000 Gel income and this can be explained by various factors. First of all the regulation about mortgage loans, which gives ability to get loan mostly people with average and high income. Table 7.

Monthly Income and Education (Crosstabulation) demonstrates people who are holding master's degree and PhD degree are having high income and this result makes us sure, that education is appreciated appropriately.

Table 7.

		Education				Total
		Bachelor	Master	PhD	Secondary education	
Monthly Income	0 – 500	2	0	0	0	2
	501 – 1000	1	3	0	0	4
	1001 – 1500	5	8	1	1	15
	1501 – 2000	10	12	3	0	25
	2000 +	10	40	7	1	58
Total		28	63	11	2	104

Note. Authors' according to the research

Table 8.

		Monthly Income					Total
		0 – 500	1001 – 1500	1501 – 2000	2000 +	501 – 1000	
Occupation	Full time	0	10	15	56	1	82
	Part time	0	3	2	1	1	7
	Self employed	0	2	8	1	1	12
	Unemployed	2	0	0	0	1	3
Total		2	15	25	58	4	104

Note. Authors' according to the research

As the Table 8. Occupation and income (Crosstabulation) show, average and high income (according to National Statistics office of Georgia, average salary in 1st Quarter is 1716.6 Gel), is having people who working full time and also those who are self-employed and this is realistic, that on Georgian labor market in order to get average and high salary you have to work full time, or you can

have your own business and be self-employed, which also gives ability of gaining average and high income.

The research participants were also asked questions about knowledge about green concept and the result showed, that 58.7% of them partially knew what does the green concept mean (see, Table 9.

Knowledge about green concept).

Table 9.

		Knowledge about green concept			
		Do you know what does the green building concept mean?			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	2	1.9	1.9	1.9
	Partially	61	58.7	58.7	60.6
	Yes	41	39.4	39.4	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors' according to the research

The study showed that 57.7% of participants are motivated to pay more if the building meets “green building” standard, besides the fact that they do not completely know what does it mean, but as various studies show, the word green itself have positive impact

on people’s decision-making process, they have feeling that they are making something good to the nature, planet and themselves (see, the Table 10.

Paying more if building meets “green building standards”).

Table 10.

Paying more if building meets “green building standards”

How motivated are you to pay more if you know the building meets "green building" standards? (1) I am completely motivated; (2) I am motivated;(3) I don't know;(4) I am not motivated; (5) I am not motivated at all 5).					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	60	57.7	57.7	57.7
	2	35	33.7	33.7	91.3
	3	7	6.7	6.7	98.1
	5	2	1.9	1.9	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Note. Authors’ according to the research

Table 11.

Green strategies influence

Do green marketing strategies have influence on you? e.g. when it is focused on the ecological environment and its profitability? (1) High impact; (2) Average impact; (3) Don't know, no answer; (4) Little impact; (5) No impact					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	58	55.8	55.8	55.8
	2	37	35.6	35.6	91.3
	3	6	5.8	5.8	97.1
	4	2	1.9	1.9	99.0
	5	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	104	100.0	100.0		

Note. Authors’ according to the research

In order to study the role of green marketing strategies participants were asked question about influence of green marketing strategies. It showed that it has high impact on them – high impact – 55.8% and average impact for 35.6% (see, Table 11.

Green strategies influence). In order to see if there in connection with education and building concept crosstabulation was done, which demonstrated, that participants who were holding master’s degree know the idea of green building concept (26%) and 35% of them partially had information.

Table 12.

Education and green building concept meaning (Crosstabulation)

		Do you know what does the green building concept mean?			Total
		No	Partially	Yes	
Education	Bachelor	0	19	9	28
	Master	2	35	26	63
	PhD	0	6	5	11
	Secondary education	0	1	1	2
Total	2	61	41	104	

Note. Authors’ according to the research

Also as the aim of the research was to study the factors of decision-making process, 11 factors were highlight and points were distributed with this way ((1) Insignificant (2) Slightly important (3) Averagely important (4) Important (5) Very important):

– Company credibility: 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 1%, 3 points by 5.8%; 4 points by 27.9% and **5 points by 64.4%**;

– Social environment: 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 1%, **3 points by 51.9%**; 4 points by 36.5% and 5 points by 9.6%;

– Ecologically clean environment: 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 2.9 %, 3 points by 1%; 4 points by 21.2% and **5 points by 74.0%**;

– Safe environment: 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 1%, 3 points by 1%; 4 points by 5.8% and 5 points by **91.3%**;

– Marketing campaign: 1 point was given by 1.9%, 2 points by 37.5%, **3 points by 46.2%**; 4 points by 10.6% and 5 points by 3.8%;

– Quality: 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 1%, 4 points by 3.8% and **5 points by 94.2%**;

– Price: 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 1.9%, 3 points by 2.9%; **4 points by 59.6 %** and 5 points by 34.6%;

– Healthy building (e.g. energy efficient blocks): 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 1%, 3 points by 6.7%; **4 points by 48.1%** and 5 points by 43.3%;

– Building architecture: 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 1.9%, **3 points by 51.9%**; 4 points by 26% and 5 points by 19.2%;

– Advice/recommendation of a competent person: 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 2.9%, 3

Points distribution between two groups, divided by income

points by 27.9%; 4 points by 32.7% and **5 points by 35.6%**;

– Location: 1 point was given by 1%, 2 points by 1%, 3 points by 1.9%; 4 points by 19.2% and **5 points by 76.9%**;

– Banking conditions: 1 point was given by 1.9%, 2 points by 4.8%, **3 points by 61.5%**; 4 points by 11.5% and 5 points by 20.2%.

In order to see if income influences on the factors the data was studied separately in two groups: one is having income more than 1501 GEL (average and more) and another is having income from 0 to 1500 GEL, as it showed (see, the Table 13).

Points distribution between two groups, divided by income) people with different income have different priorities in decision-making process.

Table 13.

Points distribution between two groups, divided by income

Group with income 1501 GEL and more	Points	Group with income 0-1500 GEL	Points
Quality	4.89	Safe environment	4.76
Safe environment	4.86	Quality	4.67
Location	4.70	Location	4.67
Ecologically clean environment	4.64	Company credibility	4.57
Company credibility	4.54	Ecologically clean environment	4.48
Healthy building	4.32	Price	4.24
Price	4.25	Healthy building	4.14
Advice/recommendation	3.99	Advice/recommendation	4.00
Building architecture	3.61	Building architecture	3.57
Social environment	3.53	Bank/loan conditions	3.57
Bank/loan conditions	3.43	Social environment	3.43
Marketing campaign	2.77	Marketing campaign	3.05
* (Scale from 1 to 5 - (1) Insignificant (2) Slightly important (3) Averagely important (4) Important (5) Very important)			

Note. Authors' according to the research

Also data was analyzed with education level too in regards of factors. The results showed, that people with different educational level have different priorities (see, Diagram 1. Factors influencing decision making process, according to education). The diagram shows, that if a person, has high income, is less interesting in banking loan conditions, but is interesting in location and

competent people recommendation. Also to the price factor people with low income is more important. Also, here can be mentioned company credibility, what is more important for the people with PhD and master's degree.

Diagram 1. Factors influencing decision making process, according to education (Scale from 1 to 5 - (1) Insignificant (2) Slightly important (3) Averagely important (4) Important (5) Very important)

Note. Authors' according to the research

Also to study if education differs people's decision-making factors from each other, each group was analyzed separately (See,

Table 14.

Factors priority according to education)

Table 14.

Factors priority according to education

Factors Priority	PhD	Factors Priority	Master
Safe environment	4.82	Quality	4.92
Quality	4.82	Safe environment	4.90
Company credibility	4.73	Location	4.75
Location	4.64	Ecologically clean environment	4.73
Ecologically clean environment	4.27	Company credibility	4.54
Price	4.18	Healthy building	4.37
Healthy building	4.09	The price	4.30
Social environment	3.73	Advice/recommendation	4.08
Building architecture	3.55	Social environment	3.54
Advice/recommendation	3.45	Bank/loan conditions	3.54
Bank/loan conditions	3.09	Building architecture	3.52
Marketing campaign	2.55	Marketing campaign	2.76
Factors Priority	Bachelor	Factors Priority	Secondary Education
Quality	4.86	Quality	5
Safe environment	4.79	Healthy building	5
Location	4.64	Company credibility	4.5
Ecologically clean environment	4.61	Safe environment	4.5
Company credibility	4.46	Ecologically clean environment	4.5
Healthy building	4.25	The price	4.5
The price	4.14	Location	4.5
Advice/recommendation	4.07	Bank/loan conditions	4
Building architecture	3.86	Social environment	3.5
Social environment	3.43	Building architecture	3
Bank/loan conditions	3.29	Advice/recommendation	3
Marketing campaign	2.89	Marketing campaign	2.5

*(scale from 1 to 5 - (1) Insignificant (2) Slightly important (3) Averagely important (4) Important (5) Very important)

Note. Authors' according to the research

Regression analysis was made in MS Excel. After testing variables on auto-correlation following variables were taken out from the model: Safe environment,

ecologically clean environment and Quality. Adjusted R² of the model is 0.4 that is acceptable

Table 15.

Regression analysis results

Regression Statistics									
Multiple R	0.676101								
R Square	0.457112								
Adjusted R Square	0.398737								
Standard Error	0.599312								
Observations	104								
ANOVA									
		df	SS	MS	F	Significance F			
Regression		10	28.1256	2.81256	7.830617	5.35E-09			
Residual		93	33.40325	0.359175					
Total		103	61.52885						
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%	
Intercept	0.961651	0.547285	1.75713	0.082187	-0.12515	2.048451	-0.12515	2.048451	
x1	0.045069	0.104765	0.430189	0.668054	-0.16297	0.253111	-0.16297	0.253111	
x2	-0.03771	0.115523	-0.32639	0.74486	-0.26711	0.191701	-0.26711	0.191701	
x5	0.136514	0.084278	1.619815	0.108658	-0.03084	0.303873	-0.03084	0.303873	
x7	0.026325	0.119503	0.220285	0.826132	-0.21099	0.263635	-0.21099	0.263635	
x8	-0.00012	0.102908	-0.0012	0.999046	-0.20448	0.204232	-0.20448	0.204232	
x9	0.239179	0.090592	2.64017	0.009718	0.059281	0.419077	0.059281	0.419077	
x10	-0.29825	0.083192	-3.58502	0.000539	-0.46345	-0.13304	-0.46345	-0.13304	
x11	-0.12549	0.114323	-1.09764	0.275195	-0.35251	0.101537	-0.35251	0.101537	
x12	0.069995	0.081968	0.853932	0.395337	-0.09278	0.232767	-0.09278	0.232767	
x13	0.466533	0.080933	5.764415	1.06E-07	0.305815	0.62725	0.305815	0.62725	

β_1 (Company trust); β_2 (Social environment); β_3 (Safe environment); β_4 (Ecologically clean environment); β_5 (Marketing campaign); β_6 (Quality); β_7 (Recommendation); β_8 (Healthier construction materials); β_9 (Architecture); β_{10} (Price); β_{11} (Location); β_{12} (Interest rate); β_{13} (Green building)

Note. Authors' according to the research

As it can be seen from the table two variables: Architecture and Price are statistically significant at 0.01 level. Results show that there is positive correlation between Architecture of the building and purchase intention, meaning that the better is satisfaction with architecture higher the intention for buying the property and it has positive effect on consumers decision making process. As for the second variable, results show that there is strong negative correlation between Price of the property and purchase intention, meaning that higher the price, lower the purchase intention and this is close

to the reality, as people are looking for price affordable real estates, but as they are motivated to buy flats in high quality buildings and are also motivated to pay more for “green buildings”, rising price on properties is sensitive case and needs clear communication with target segments, that will make sure customers, that high price is caused by specific factors, what is deeply related with consumers well-being.

On behalf of the carried research we can demonstrate the profile of potential consumer and it looks so:

Table 16.

The profile of potential consumer

Gender	Male/female
Age:	35-44
Education	Master's degree
Occupation	Working Full time
Number of family members	2
Willing to pay more for green building	Yes
Factors	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Safe environment 2. Quality 3. Company credibility 4. Location 5. Ecologically clean environment 6. Price 7. Healthy building 8. Social environment 9. Building architecture 10. Advice/recommendation 11. Bank/loan conditions 12. Marketing campaign

Note. Authors' according to the research

As the results show, for the consumers living in a safe environment is crucially important, then comes quality and this is very close to current challenges, because while purchasing something and especially real estate, investing money in good quality buildings is very important, then comes company's credibility which creates trust and is related with company image. Marketing campaigns are also highly appreciated, but as we are facing greenwashing problems, sometimes people prefer to rely more on competent person/expert recommendation rather than marketing campaign, so customers check and analyze everything after attracting their attention with marketing campaigns and their choice is not depended only marketing activities.

Conclusions

The hypothesis of the study stating that green marketing has a positive effect on the purchase intentions of Georgian consumers in the construction industry was supported partly in the given study, as green marketing strategies have influence on consumers, but when marketing as a factor was given in the decision-making factor list, it appeared not to be so important as e.g. quality. One main reason for this could be lack of awareness about green buildings and sustainability and less interest towards these topics among Georgian customer and another fact can be greenwashing, where consumers do not trust marketing campaigns. Also, study showed price as an important factor influencing purchase intention that is quite logical especially for developing country like Georgia. Architecture of the building seems to be important factor affecting decision of Georgian customers in the construction sector that is logical as well since there are huge variety of styles nowadays that are used in construction industry in Georgia.

As more than half of the respondents did not know what does the concept of green building mean, that's why marketing campaigns may not be so affective. Here we can see, that before campaigns raising awareness, spreading information about green building concepts and highlight its importance is essentially important.

If the companies want to implement green marketing in their businesses, they must first ensure their products genuinely offer environmental benefits. Misleading claims can lead to "greenwashing", which can damage a brand's reputation. Clear and reliable communication about the environmental benefits of the products is paramount.

To sum up, as environmental and ecological concerns continue to influence consumer and business choices and behavior, the future of green marketing is bright and promising. Businesses that can effectively promote their eco-friendly and healthy buildings stand to gain not just increased sales, but also a positive brand image, trust and customer loyalty.

In conclusion, green marketing represents an exciting and challenging opportunity for businesses in the construction industry. On behalf of green marketing strategies, businesses can cater to the growing demand for sustainable products and contribute to a greener future.

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Appendix

Filter Question: Do you have an intention to buy a house?

- Yes
- No

1. Gender:

Male

Female

2. Age

18-24

25-34

35-44

45-54

55+

3. Education

Secondary education

Bachelor

Master

PhD

4. Occupation

Full time

Part time

Self employed

Unemployed

5. Number of family members

I live alone

1

2

3

4

5 and more

6. Monthly income

0 – 500

501 – 1000

1001 – 1500

1501 – 2000

2000 +

7. Do you know what does the green building concept mean?

Yes

No

Partially

8. In the decision-making process, how did you prioritize the following factors?

(1) Insignificant (2) Slightly important (3) Averagely important (4) Important (5) Very important

Company credibility

Social environment

Safe environment

Ecologically clean environment

Marketing campaign

Quality

Advice/recommendation of a competent person

Healthy building (e.g. energy efficient blocks)

Building architecture

The price

Location

Bank/loan conditions (e.g. loans rate).

9. How motivated are you to pay more if you know the building meets "green building" standards? ((1) I am completely motivated; (2) I am motivated; (3) I don't know; (4) I am not motivated; (5) I am not motivated at all 5).

10. Do green marketing strategies have influence on you? e.g. when it is focused on the ecological environment and its profitability?

(1) High impact; (2) Average impact; (3) Don't know, no answer; (4) Little impact; (5) No impact